

THE PRINCIPLE OF VERTICALIZATION AND THE TEACHING WORK OF PROFESSIONAL EDUCATION TEACHERS

EL PRINCIPIO DE VERTICALIZACIÓN Y LA LABOR DOCENTE DE LOS DOCENTES EN LA EDUCACIÓN PROFESIONAL

O PRINCÍPIO DA VERTICALIZAÇÃO E O TRABALHO DOCENTE DOS PROFESSORES DA EDUCAÇÃO PROFISSIONAL

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Abstract

This article presents an analysis of academic productions on the relationship between the principle of verticalization and teaching work. searches were carried out in digital databases that gather theses and dissertations and annals of two events in the field of education. The search for theses and dissertations was carried out in the Theses and Dissertations Catalog of the CAPES and in the BDTD of the IBICT, and the annals of the events were consulted on the bases of the ANPED and the Symposiums of the ANPAE. As advanced search descriptors, the exact terms “Federal Institutes”, “Teaching Work” and “Verticalization” were combined with each other, and the period from 2008 to 2019 was used as a filter. In all, 17 works were identified, including seven dissertations, five theses and five articles published in annals of events, thus constituting the set of analyzed productions. The mapping showed that the topic of teaching work and the verticalization of professional education is recent, with different thematic approaches (teacher training, working conditions, democratization of access to higher education, and the expansion of technical professional education), thus indicating the need for expansion of studies in this perspective.

Keywords: Teaching Work; Federal Institutes; Verticalization.

Resumen

Este artículo presenta un análisis de producciones académicas sobre la relación entre el principio de verticalización en los Institutos Federales y el trabajo docente. Las búsquedas se realizaron en bases de datos digitales que reúnen tesis y disertaciones y anales de dos eventos en el campo de la educación. Las bases de datos digitales de tesis y disertaciones utilizadas fueron el

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Catálogo de Tesis y Disertaciones de la Coordinación de Perfeccionamiento del Personal de Educación Superior (CAPES) y la Biblioteca Digital Brasileña de Tesis y Disertaciones (BDTD) del Instituto Brasileño de Información en Ciencia y Tecnología (IBICT). Los anales de los eventos fueron consultados sobre las bases de los Encuentros Científicos Nacionales de la Asociación Nacional de Posgrado e Investigación en Educación (ANPED) y los Simposios de la Asociación Nacional de Política y Administración Educativa (ANPAE). Como descriptores de búsqueda avanzada, se combinaron los términos exactos “Institutos Federales”, “Obra Docente” y “Verticalización”, y se utilizó como filtro el período de 2008 a 2019. En total, se identificaron 17 obras, incluidas siete disertaciones, cinco tesis y cinco artículos publicados en anales de sucesos, constituyendo así el conjunto de producciones analizadas. El mapeo mostró que el tema del trabajo docente y la verticalización de la formación profesional es reciente, con diferentes abordajes temáticos (formación docente, condiciones de trabajo, democratización del acceso a la educación superior y expansión de la formación profesional técnica), indicando así la necesidad de ampliación de los estudios en esta perspectiva.

Palabras clave: Trabajo Docente; Institutos Federales; Verticalización.

Resumo

Este artigo apresenta uma análise das produções acadêmicas sobre a relação entre o princípio da verticalização nos Institutos Federais e o trabalho docente. As buscas foram realizadas em bases digitais de dados que reúnem teses e dissertações, além de anais de dois eventos da área de educação. As bases digitais de teses e dissertações utilizadas foram o Catálogo de Teses e Dissertações da Coordenação de Aperfeiçoamento de Pessoal de Nível Superior (CAPES) e a Biblioteca Digital Brasileira de Teses e Dissertações (BDTD) do Instituto Brasileiro de Informação em Ciência e Tecnologia (IBICT). Os anais dos eventos foram consultados nas páginas virtuais das Reuniões Científicas Nacionais da Associação Nacional de Pós-Graduação e Pesquisa em Educação (ANPED) e dos Simpósios da Associação Nacional de Política e Administração da Educação (ANPAE). Foram estabelecidos como descritores de busca avançada os termos exatos “Institutos Federais”, “Trabalho Docente” e “Verticalização” combinados entre si, cujo recorte temporal compreendeu o período de 2008 a 2019. Ao todo foram identificados 17 trabalhos, entre eles sete dissertações, cinco teses e cinco artigos publicados em anais de eventos, constituindo-se, assim, o conjunto das produções analisadas. O mapeamento demonstrou que o tema trabalho docente e verticalização da educação profissional é recente, com abordagens temáticas diversas (formação de professores, condição de trabalho, democratização do acesso ao ensino superior, e a ampliação da educação profissional técnica), indicando, portanto, a necessidade de ampliação de estudos nessa perspectiva.

Palavras-chave: Trabalho Docente; Institutos Federais; Verticalização.

Introduction

In the first decade of the 2000s, Brazil went down a path of changes in educational policies that resulted in changes in the way public policies for vocational and technological education were thought of and implemented in the country. These changes had consequences for the work of teachers in this type of education. In this

context of change, the Federal Institutes of Education, Science and Technology are the most recent materialization of public policies in professional education in Brazil. According to Article 2 of Law 11.892/2008 (Brasil, 2008), the Federal Institutes (IFs) are institutions of higher, basic and professional education, multi-curricular and *multi-campus*, specialized in offering professional and technological education in the different types of education, this education is based on the combination of technical and technological knowledge with their pedagogical practices. The Federal Institutes cover the entire national territory, according to the Ministry of Education (MEC) website³, in 2019, they comprise "[...] more than 661 units, which are linked to 38 Federal Institutes, 02 Federal Technological Education Centers (Cefet), the Federal Technological University of Paraná (UTFPR), 22 technical schools linked to federal universities and Colégio Pedro II".

The institutional framework of the IFs proposes differentiated teaching when it encourages the "integration" and "verticalization" of basic education with professional education, as well as the articulation between teaching, research and extension, with the same teaching staff and in the same educational environment.

Integration involves bringing together different stages and modalities of national education focused on professional, technical and technological education in the same environment, while also sharing pedagogical proposals. Verticalization, on the other hand, means that, in addition to integration, training itineraries are established that run from technical courses to doctorates.

As a principle for organizing curricular components, verticalization implies the recognition of flows that allow the construction of training itineraries between the different professional and technological education courses: professional qualification, technical, undergraduate and postgraduate technological, introducing a dynamic of teaching work and institutional organization of education, hitherto unprecedented in national public educational policy.

Verticalization materializes in teaching work since this process requires teachers to work in different stages and modalities of education simultaneously and in the same

³ Available at: < <http://portal.mec.gov.br/rede-federal-inicial/instituicoes>>. Accessed on Nov 25, 2019.

institution. In this chain, verticalization permeates the teaching environment and raises questions about teachers' perspectives on their role in this process, because teachers' work is directly related to the education of individuals in the school environment. This makes it clear that it is important to study the relationship between teaching work and verticalization, in terms of teacher training, working conditions, democratization of access and the expansion of professional and technical education.

A bibliographic study carried out in digital databases and catalogs of theses and dissertations, as well as in the annals of events of two scientific associations in education, sought to verify what has been researched and disseminated regarding the relationship between verticalization and teaching work in the FIs.

The digital databases used for the mapping were the following: Catalog of Theses and Dissertations of the Coordination for the Improvement of Higher Education Personnel (CAPES), Brazilian Digital Library of Theses and Dissertations (BDTD) of the Brazilian Institute of Information in Science and Technology (IBICT), Proceedings of National Scientific Meetings of the National Association for Graduate Studies and Research in Education (ANPED) and Proceedings of National Symposia of the National Association for Research in Education (ANPAE).

Using tables and charts, it was possible to organize the mapping of scientific production to carry out the analysis of the productions identified, initially technical and then epistemological.

For the technical analysis, in addition to quantifying the results, the following criteria were also adopted: the preponderant regions of production and the *locus* of preference of the research. For the epistemological analysis, we considered the methodology used in the research and, subsequently, the results obtained through the questions raised.

The time frame defined was between 2008 and 2019. The year 2008 was used as a reference because the Federal Network for Professional and Technological Education and the Federal Institutes (IFs) were inaugurated in that year, as was the enactment of Law No. 11,892, which established the IFs. As search descriptors, the terms

"verticalization", "teaching work" and "Federal Institutes" were defined, in quotation marks and connected by the Boolean term AND.

In the CAPES digital database, the following filters were used: Major Knowledge Area (Human Sciences), Knowledge Area (Education); Evaluation Area (Education); Concentration Area (Education). In the BDTD/IBICT, the survey was carried out using the advanced search tool.

In order to choose the papers published in the ANPED meeting annals, we defined the location of the search descriptors in the keywords, abstracts and titles of the papers presented in the working groups (WG) WG05 - State and Educational Policy, WG08 - Teacher Training, WG09 - Work and Education and WG11 - Higher Education Policy.

The choice of WG05 considered studies and research on public policies in the educational sphere, as well as their formulation and implementation, which prompts discussion on the implementation of the Federal Institutes. WG08 was selected due to its proximity to the theme of the process of building, developing and deepening the knowledge needed to exercise the profession of teaching, its impacts and results, and is therefore directly related to teaching work. WG09, in turn, deals with discussions on the relationship between the world of work and education, and therefore on the expansion of professional education with the creation of the Federal Institutes. The same goes for WG11, which studies and discusses higher education policies, given that the FIs also offer this type of education. These WGs analyzed the eight annals of national meetings that took place between 2008 and 2019.

Regarding the searches carried out in the ANPAE National Symposium Proceedings, five symposiums were analyzed. Unlike ANPED, ANPAE organizes its proceedings along axes that change with each edition of the event. The search was therefore carried out on the following symposia: XXIV Symposium (2009); XXV Symposium (2011); XXVI Symposium (2013), XXVII Symposium (2015) and XXVIII Symposium (2017).

Using the descriptors and criteria defined, a total of 38 productions were found, of which 25 are theses and dissertations, while 13 are papers from events, broken down by type and source, as shown in Table 1 below:

Chart 1 - Scientific productions on verticalization and teaching at Federal Institutes (2008 - 2009).

Descriptors	Sources	Type of production	Quantity
"Teaching work" AND "Verticalization" AND "Federal Institutes"	CAPES	Dissertations	8
		Thesis	5
	IBICT	Dissertations	8
		Thesis	4
	ANPED		2
	ANPAE		11
Total			38

Source: Created by the authors with data from: CAPES, IBICT, ANPED e ANPAE (2024).

Of the 25 academic productions located in the theses and dissertations category, four dissertations and two theses are repeated, both in IBICT and CAPES. That said, the total number of studies in this category is 19. However, when the abstracts of the academic productions and event papers were re-screened, it was found that, of the total of 32, only 17 productions (12 theses and dissertations, as well as five papers published in event proceedings) actually met the criterion of analyzing the relationship between teaching work and verticalization in the FIs. Thus, 17 were the total number of articles analyzed in this text, as shown in Tables 2 and 3 below:

Chart 2 – Thesis and Dissertations on teaching work and verticalization in the FIs.

Type of production	Title	Author	Years	Institution
Dissertation	The process of verticalization of professional and technological education and its implications for the quality of work of teachers at the São Vicente do Sul Campus of the Farroupilha Federal Institute	FERNANDES, Maria Regina da Silva	12/03/2013	UFRRJ
	Teaching at the Federal Institute of the Triângulo Mineiro (IFTM): Uberaba Campus 2009 to 2013	GENTIL, Ana Maria Fonseca	20/08/2015	UNIUBE
	Verticalization in the Federal Institutes of Education, Science and Technology: Conception(s) and challenges in the IFRS.	QUEVEDO, Margarete	04/03/2016	UCS

Type of production	Title	Author	Years	Institution
	Teaching work in the verticalization of the Federal Institute of Brasilia	OLIVEIRA, Blenda Cavalcante de	06/10/2016	UnB
	Teaching work in the context of vertical education at the Rio Verde Campus of the Goiano Federal Institute: limits and possibilities for emancipatory education	DOURADO, Adaildes Bispo	17/08/2018	UFG
	The verticalization of teaching and its effectson the work of teachers at the Federal Institute of Ceará - Campus Crato	TAVARES, Amanda de Aquino	27/11/2018	UFRRJ
	The organization of pedagogical work at theFederal Institute of Paraná - Palmas campus:implications for teaching work	PERATZ, Tatiane	28/02/2019	UNIOEST
Thesis	New meanings of curricular policies for professional education at the Federal Institute of Rio Grande do Sul	ARAUJO, Jair Jonko	25/09/2013	UFPEL
	Tensions and Perspectives of the Federal Network in the field of professional and technological education: a study of the IF goiano in the ceres and rio verde campuses - Goiás	BOAVENTURA, Géisa D'Ávila Ribeiro	04/08/2016	PUC-GO
	The precariousness of teacher training for basic education at the Federal Institute of Science, Education and Technology of Acre -Cruzeiro do Sul Campus	ARAUJO, José Cesar do Nascimento	05/03/2018	UFAM
	Federal Institutes of Education, Science andTechnology from the perspective of institutional innovation: a study of a theoretical-empirical model in the light of institutional indicators	ÁVILA, Carlos Alberto de	23/03/2018	UNB
	Flexible Teacher in the verticalized teaching of the Federal Institute of Education, Scienceand Technology of Rio de Janeiro - IFR: a lookat the Federal Network of Technical and Technological Education in times of flexible accumulation	SILVA, Katia Correia da	05/04/2018	UFPR

Source: prepared by the researchers with data from the CAPES Theses and Dissertations Database and BDTD/IBICT (2019).

As for the papers published in annals, of the 13 articles initially selected, five were chosen for analysis due to their proximity to the object of study, two from ANPED and three from ANPAE, which is described in Table 3 below:

Chart 3 - Articles published in ANPED and ANPAE event annals.

Association	Year	Title	Author	WT or Axis
ANPED	2015	Teacher training at the Federal Institutes: an identity yet to be built	Ângela Flach – IFRS – Câmpus Porto Alegre/Mari Margarete dos Santos Forster – UNISINOS	GT08
	2015	Federal Institutes and identity crisis: the case of IFC - Campus Rio do Sul	Moacir Gubert Tavares – IFC – Campus Rio do Sul	GT11
ANPAE	2015	The influence of professional and technological education policies on the Federal Institute of Ceará: from its creation to the reforms implemented by the Lula da Silva government	Nilene Matos Trigueiro	1
	2017	The expansion of higher education in the professional and technological education network in Brazil: an analysis of the results of the Federal Institute of Education, Science and Technology of Espírito Santo	Francisco José Soares Costa	2
	2017	(De) Construction of Teaching Work in the cooperation agreement between the IFSP and SEE-SP	Cíntia Magno Brazorotto/Rosemary Mattos	1

Source: prepared by the researchers with data from the ANPED and ANPAE event annals (2019).

Looking at the postgraduate programs in which the theses and dissertations were defended, it is possible to see that four productions are linked to programs located in the Midwest, three in the Southeast, three in the South and one in the North. Apart from three, the other institutions are public. UFRRJ and UNB have two productions each, while all the others have just one production on the subject.

As for the institutional affiliation of the authors of the published works, four are full professors at the Federal Institutes of the *campuses where they carried out their research*, another two are pedagogues, one from the Federal Institute of the *campus where she carried out the research* and another pedagogue from the São Paulo State Secretary of Education, as well as another author who is a full professor at a private higher education institution.

Regarding the *locus* of the research, it was observed that of the twelve theses and dissertations, nine were carried out in the same regions where the postgraduate programs are located. About the other studies, two were defended at the UFRRJ (Southeast region) and researched the Farroupilha Federal Institute - São Vicente do Sul

Campus, located in the South of the country, while the other at the Federal Institute of Ceará. The work defended at UFPR, located in the South region, investigates the Rio de Janeiro Institute, located in the Southeast region.

It is worth noting that, of Brazil's five regions, only the Northeast has no postgraduate program that presents research results related to the topic.

About the methodology used in the theses and dissertations, of the 12 theses and dissertations selected, two do not specify the method⁴. Of the 10 that do make the method clear, seven are based on the framework of Dialectical Historical Materialism (DHM) as a research approach and three claim to be descriptive research with qualitative objectives.

About the data collection instruments used, 10 studies used questionnaires (with questions that included open and closed answers) and semi-structured interviews, while one, in addition to these instruments, also used focus groups. Of these 10, eight had teachers from the study sites as their research subjects, while one had, in addition to teachers, administrative technicians in education and students (in course and graduates) as its subjects. In another, the subjects were not only teachers, but also those who held management positions in the institution (pro-rectors, systemic directors, advisors, campus general directors, directors and heads of teaching, research and extension departments).

Only three papers present bibliographical research on the subject, two dissertations and one thesis. They used the terms Teacher Work, Technological Professional Education, Verticalization, Professional Education, Federal Institutes and Teacher Training Policies as search descriptors.

Regarding the papers published at the events, the types of research used were case studies, bibliographical research, bibliographical-documentary research and documentary research. Of the five articles analyzed, only one made clear the method adopted (in this case, the MHD). The studies that carried out fieldwork used semi-structured interviews as the data collection technique.

⁴ One of them, CAPES, informs us that the text is not authorized for publication.

What do the research says

The productions analyze the relationship between verticalization and teaching work from two perspectives: the analysis of the quality of the work done by the teacher and the results achieved by the students, as well as the analysis of the public educational policies that established the FIs.

Table 4 below shows the issues/problems of each paper.

Chart 4 - Issues/problems of the scientific productions analyzed.

Type of production	Question/Problem	Author
Dissertation	How does the process of verticalization of teaching influence the quality of teaching?	FERNANDES, Maria Regina da Silva
	How do the teachers at the Uberaba Campus perceive and analyze their work since the transformation of the then CEFET - Uberaba into IFTM in 2008, when the institutional and pedagogical reconfigurations took place there?	GENTIL, Ana Maria Fonseca
	Understand the concept(s) of verticalization of basic education to professional education and higher education within the Federal Institute of Education, Science and Technology of Rio Grande do Sul (IFRS)	QUEVEDO, Margarete
	What are the constituent elements of teaching work in the verticalization of the Federal Institute of Brasilia?	OLIVEIRA, Blenda Cavalcante de
	Whether the verticalization of education at the Federal Institutes is a possibility for consolidating an educational structure capable of training individuals, or whether it is yet another structure designed to offer instrumental education, based on the neoliberal policies that have been articulated in Brazil and around the world with the aim of strengthening capital.	DOURADO, Adaildes Bispo
	What are the effects of the process of verticalization of education in the Federal Institutes on the work of teachers at IFCE Crato?	TAVARES, Amanda de Aquino
How is pedagogical work organized at the Federal Institute of Paraná - Palmas Campus and what are the implications for teaching?	PERATZ, Tatiane	
Thesis	What new meanings are constructed in IFSul's curriculum policy with the transformation into a Federal Institute?	ARAUJO, Jair Jonko
	How has Law 11.892/2008, bringing new possibilities for shaping the courses of the Federal Institutes, been remaking the field of professional education and the habits of agents - teachers and managers in the new organization of spaces of power?	BOAVENTURA, Géisa D'Ávila Ribeiro
	What mechanisms and processes cause the precariousness of teacher training for basic education in the Mathematics Degree program at the Federal Institute of Acre - Cruzeiro do Sul Campus (2011 - 2015)?	ARAUJO, José Cesar do Nascimento

Type of production	Question/Problem	Author
	-	SILVA, Katia Correia da
Article	To understand the process of implementing bachelor's degree courses in the IFs, taking as an object of analysis a bachelor's degree course at a Federal Institute located in the south of Brazil.	FLACH, Ângela/FOSTER, Maria Margarete dos Santos
	To verify the characteristics of this new institutional identity, especially with regard to the inseparability of teaching, research and extension, which characterize the university "model".	TAVARES, Moacir Gubert
	The influence of professional and technological education policies on the Federal Institute of Ceará: from its creation to the reforms implemented by the Lula da Silva government	TRIGUEIRO, Nilene Matos
	The expansion of higher education in the professional and technological education network in Brazil: an analysis of the results of the Federal Institute of Education, Science and Technology of Espírito Santo	COSTA, Francisco José Soares
	(Un)Construction of Teaching Work in the cooperation agreement between the IFSP and SEE-SP (Un)Construction of Teaching Work in the cooperation agreement between the IFSP and SEE-SP	BRAZOROTTO, Cíntia Magno/MATTOS, Rosemary

Source: prepared by the authors with data collected from the CAPES Theses and Dissertations Database, BDTD/IBICT and ANPED and ANPAE event annals (2024).

The studies show similar results. According to the research, teachers find it difficult to cope with the model of verticalization of teaching proposed by the IFs. This difficulty stems from what they call "fragmentation", resulting from the intensification of work, since it causes overload and reflects on the meaning teachers give to their work, as well as on the establishment of their teaching identity. In other words, the verticalization of work would increase its intensity, reducing rest time and incorporating more actions, given the increase in the size and complexity of the working day and the flexibility of teaching action. The studies also have in common results that point to the need to implement a process of continuing training for teachers, which should be extended to pedagogical staff, in order to minimize the difficulties faced, both in the planning and development of courses, and in vertical teaching work.

Despite the difficulties pointed out, in general, the participants in the surveys said they were satisfied with the transformation of the schools into FIs, because, for them,

this meant access for a greater number of students, the opening up of competitions and new jobs.

According to Flack and Foster (2015, p. 16),

As I was able to see in this study, the subjects interviewed here, although aware of the great difficulties they face on a daily basis, were motivated and hopeful about their work, dealing optimistically with the challenges facing the degree course in which they work.

Also according to Tavares (2015, p. 16, emphasis added), "the interviews revealed the factor that contributes significantly to distinguishing the functions performed by the FIs and the universities: the *diversification of teaching levels, modalities, programs and areas of offer of the courses of the institution investigated*".

The Federal Institutes are among the institutions responsible for developing public policies in professional education in Brazil. They operate from secondary technical education to postgraduate studies. However, this research has shown that there are challenges to consolidating these policies, given the need to broaden the debates developed in research on teaching work and the verticalization of professional education.

Final considerations

The subject of the relationship between teaching work and the verticalization of professional education is fairly recent, since it formally began at the end of 2008, with the law creating the Federal Institutes. It is therefore a subject that has yet to be studied.

Therefore, the literature review on the relationship between teaching work and verticalization, as a specific educational *praxis* of the FIs, indicates that over the last decade there have been few debates on this subject. Different studies have been carried out, which have focused on the category of work, teacher training and their working conditions, the democratization of access to higher education, as well as the expansion of professional and technical education.

The Federal Institutes, being the most recent materialization of public policies in professional education in Brazil, as well as offering centers with a *sine qua non* characteristic, since they operate from secondary technical education to postgraduate studies, still face challenges in their consolidation, and therefore need to expand the debates developed in research.

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